

Third Annual HPC RSE BoF

RSECon24

Andrew Turner Nick Brown Marion Weinzierl Ed Hone
Eirini Zormpa Tuomas Koskela

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE

IMPERIAL

Agenda

- 09.30-09.35** Welcome and Introduction
- 09.35-10.05** Technical/exascale presentations
- 10.05-10.35** Technical/exascale panel
- 10.35-10.45** HPC Service lightning updates
- 10.45-11.00** Break/Posters
- 11.00-11.30** Community/training presentations
- 11.30-12.00** Community/training panel
- 12.00-12.30** Wrap up & Next steps

Code of Conduct

- Be respectful, welcoming and inclusive
- Do not disrupt or interrupt
- No violence
- No sexist, racist, homophobic, transphobic, ableist, or exclusionary jokes or remarks
- Otherwise you will be asked to leave

Chatham House Rule for the Discussions

“When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the **Chatham House Rule**, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.”

Means: Talk about the “what”, but not about the “who from where”.

What happened so far?

- “ExCALIBUR RSEs meet HPC Champions” event after RSECon22
 - Andy, Marion, Jemma
- HPC RSE BoF at RSECon23
 - Andy, Marion, Ed
- Online meet-up March 2024
 - Andy, Marion, Ed, Nick
- No we have a team of six: Andy, Marion, Ed, Nick, Eirini, Tuomas
- Working on
 - Organising meet-ups and events like this
 - Online presence/signpost to groups and initiatives
 - Becoming a SocRSE Special Interest Group
 - Being more inclusive

Next Steps

- Fill in your stickies and stick to the wall on your way out!
 - Green sticky: something you enjoyed about the session or want to see more of
 - Red sticky: something that could be improved or added
- Thanks to everyone for contributing!
- If you want to get involved with the HPC RSE orga team, grab one of us here, on Slack, or send us an email!
- We will summarise outcome of this meeting in a blog post.
- We will work on becoming an HPC RSE Special Interest Group under SocRSE
- We will organise an online meet-up over winter
- We will get in touch on Slack, Mastodon, ExCALIBUR mailing lists,...